

WAYS OF INTERNAL AUDIT AND INCREASE EFFICIENCY IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS

N.D. Makhmudova

is a teacher of “TIAME” NRU

+998 99 806 14 08, makhmudovanargiza1408@gmail.com

Abstract: *In the article discussed ways in which internal audit in budget organization, the goals and objectives of internal audit, the principles of accounting in budgetary organization, methods of checking the units under review, approaches have been explored.*

Key words: *budget organization, internal audit, audit methods, effectiveness, auditor, quality, evaluation, disciplined approach, risk, asset, state ownership.*

In our country, the normative legal and methodological basis of auditing was formed, as well as a simplified and indefinite system of auditing activity licensing was introduced, which made it possible to form the market of auditing services and ensure the entry of local auditing organizations into large international networks of auditing companies. The development of an effective system of internal audit is carried out on the basis of existing laws in society. Management staff and internal auditors make decisions in monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the internal control system. Internal audit service can be applied to any type of enterprise and organization, regardless of its structure. Only in budgetary organizations, internal audit requires changing the methods of its activity and sets several requirements for the organization of effective internal control.

First of all, in order to effectively organize the internal audit service in budget organizations, we need to clearly define its purpose. In order to effectively organize internal audit in budget organizations, we can set the following goals [2]:

- providing minimum value in risk reduction;
- increase the efficiency of the organization;
- ensuring that the organization's assets are used and protected from damage;
- ensuring reliability of internal and external financial reports;
- increase efficiency of use of state property;
- ensuring targeted use of budget funds;
- ensuring compliance with laws and regulations.

The laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan define the main tasks of the internal audit, and without deviating from them, we found it necessary to mention the following tasks of the internal auditor, developed in a more comprehensive manner [1]:

- independent analysis and assessment of all processes occurring in the organization;

- audit of financial statements, analysis of reliability and assessment of timely execution;
- minimization of the taxable base;
- to help the management of the organization in the management of employees;
- organization of unification and standardization of accounting processes;
- drawing up and approving a one-year plan for the implementation of internal audit for the budget organization;
- to conduct continuous inspections in all departments of the organization in accordance with the approved plan;
- control of the execution of estimated costs;
- monitoring the safety and efficiency of the organization's assets;
- constant control of the organization's income and expenses;
- to identify deficiencies in the organization's debtor and creditor debt and take measures to eliminate them;
- analysis of debts and providing operational instructions for debt reduction;
- recommendations that reduce the level of risk and possible losses when concluding contracts;
- identification and analysis of internal risks in the implementation of new projects;
- preparing the organization for external control;
- preparation of internal reports and summaries for each month.

One of the main conditions for the effective organization of the internal audit service is to clearly define the audit methods, audit plan, program, sequence, principles, along with all goals and tasks before its implementation. Internal audit activities contribute to the achievement of the organization's objectives by introducing a systematic disciplined approach to evaluating and improving the effectiveness of management, risk management and control processes. A disciplined approach is seen in the internal audit service correctly defining its goals, principles of tasks, well-planned plans, methods, and sequence of actions. Internal audit in the organization should be organized based on the following principles:

- the principle of legislation - implementation of the internal audit without deviating from the laws and norms and following the normative documents of the established procedure;
- the principle of independence - independent approach to one's tasks when conducting an internal audit in the organization;
- the principle of objectivity - in the implementation of internal control, the use of information based on specific documents in an orderly manner, organization on the basis of legislation, ways of using methods, providing complete and reliable information;

- the principle of responsibility - to be considered responsible for ineffective controls in the internal audit of the organization on the basis of the established legislation;
- the principle of systematicity - the application of comprehensively developed measures in conducting an internal audit in the organization and the implementation of its connection with the management system.

The internal audit plan in budget and budgetary organizations differs from other organizations in that the working group does not participate in this plan. Because in budget organizations, the internal auditor is organized in 1 state unit and performs the control himself. The sequence of conducting an internal audit for budget organizations, the methods used, and the order of individual audits carried out by accounting departments are roughly presented in the following table:

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No	Departments to be internal audited			
	Name of the section to be checked	Inspection period	Inspection period	Inspection methods
1	Checking the accounting of material assets	Every quarter	At the end of the quarter	Inventory, control, measurement
2	Check payroll and payroll issues	Every quarter	At the end of the quarter	Induction deduction
3	Checking the operation of the cash register and cash register operations	Every month	On the last day of the month	Inventory, comparison, scanning
4	Verification of debtor and creditor debts	Every month	On the last day of the month	Compare, contrast, analyze
5	Verification of bank related documents and money transfers	Every month	On the last day of the month	Arithmetic check, comparison
6	Inspection of contracts concluded on the basis of tender	Every month	On the last day of the month	Modeling, scanning
7	Checking the reliability of financial statements	Every quarter	End of the quarter	Arithmetic check, logical check

Each department in the accounting of the organization has its own registers, document forms, accounts, and it is recommended to check each department separately and use specific methods. In the control of the material department, accounting of material values, receipt, documents related to suppliers of goods, power of attorney, calculation of wear and tear on fixed assets, storage and technical safety of goods and material reserves, existence of contracts with materially responsible persons and list of materially responsible persons, material department

Checks are carried out sequentially to ensure that the accountant fulfills his duties correctly and does not deviate from the law, that all material assets are inventoried, all types of documents related to material assets and their analytical and synthetic accounting are properly maintained. In the calculation of wages and checks of transactions related to wages, tables that control the arrival of employees to work, sick sheets, orders to go on maternity leave, calculation of the amount of water, information on the allocation of financial assistance, deductions from wages, the correct calculation of pension amounts, vacation applications, hiring and firing orders are checked for proper handling. When checking the calculations related to the business trip, the order for the employee to go on a business trip, documents confirming the expenses of the business trip, if there are no documents confirming the travel expenses, the expenses of the business trip are calculated according to the law, and the account is kept correctly. In order to check the operation of the cash register and cash register operations, the inventory is carried out mainly in the cash register, cash receipt and outgoing orders, deposited sums, documents kept in the cash register, invoices, cash book and all types of work are carried out within the law. An internal auditor is required to check the accounts receivable and payable, as it is sometimes difficult to eliminate deficiencies in this department. Monthly and quarterly turnover statements of the organization, overdue debtor and creditor debts, calculation of transactions related to utility payments, conclusion of additional agreements, control of comparative documents, delivery of services provided under contracts, release of balances at the end of each month, elimination of debts it is necessary to check that the measures have been developed, that analytical and synthetic accounts are kept correctly, and that they are recorded in the memorial warrant and the general book. These works begin with the study of existing documents in a certain sequence, compared, contrasted and analyzed. The validity of transferred funds is confirmed by contracts, payment requests, payment orders, It is controlled by invoices and other documents. The incoming funds are classified according to their purpose, rent payments, sums returned from rejected contracts and attached to budget and non-budget accounts according to their respective purposes. Taking into account the changes made in the inspection of contracts concluded on the basis of tenders, studying whether they are organized correctly within the framework of the law, posting announcements on the site, commission payments, fulfillment of contract terms, categorization of contract amounts, terms of contracts being transferred on the basis of electronic stores, stock exchanges and tenders are monitored and studied. . When checking the reliability of financial statements, the internal audit service must analyze the components of the financial statement separately. Using various audit methods, the correctness of the report, the reliability of the data, the implementation of the budget and extra-budgetary funds, and the

comparison of cash costs are controlled. When checking the implementation of the budget, it is studied and analyzed whether the funds are used according to the plan on a monthly, quarterly basis, budget funds are used according to the plan, mainly extra-budgetary funds are included in the case of unplanned expenses. Summarizes the learned information and prepares a general conclusion. In the process of analysis, it assesses the stability and efficiency indicators of the organization. Internal audit ensures the continuous tasks of the organization, making the right management decisions in case of uncertainties, changing the economic potential of the organization in its development, and the effectiveness of the movement of the organization's indicators and risks. Every quarter, it is studied and analyzed whether the funds are used according to the plan, the budget funds are used according to the set plan, mainly extra-budgetary funds, if there are unplanned expenses. Summarizes the learned information and prepares a general conclusion. In the process of analysis, it assesses the stability and efficiency indicators of the organization. Internal audit ensures the continuous tasks of the organization, making the right management decisions in case of uncertainties, changing the economic potential of the organization in its development, and the effectiveness of the movement of the organization's indicators and risks. Every quarter, it is studied and analyzed whether the funds are used according to the plan, the budget funds are used according to the set plan, mainly extra-budgetary funds, if there are unplanned expenses. Summarizes the learned information and prepares a general conclusion. In the process of analysis, it assesses the stability and efficiency indicators of the organization. Internal audit ensures the continuous tasks of the organization, making the right management decisions in case of uncertainties, changing the economic potential of the organization in its development, and the effectiveness of the movement of the organization's indicators and risks.

In conclusion, in order to organize an effective internal audit service in budget organizations, it is necessary to carefully plan the control, to develop a method of checking based on the plan for budget organizations. The careful development of the internal audit methodology will greatly help not only the internal auditor, but also the financial control staff in the work process. Because effectively organized internal audit information is reliable. Internal audit information is widely used in state financial control. Because the internal auditor conducts continuous activities in the organization, analyzes and controls how the work is organized, the work progress of departments with errors and deficiencies. If we look at the global practice, we see that a lot of attention is paid to the internal audit system, its organization and management. Because the internal audit is constantly analyzing the organization, we can see the high efficiency indicators. Conducting each department of the organization within the framework of the established laws, taking into account its

specific aspects, ensuring that each employee is responsible for his position, and developing measures to eliminate identified shortcomings serve as an important factor in increasing efficiency.

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